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NANOTECHNOLOGY IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES – FUTURE PROSPECTS IN ORO DISPERSABLE DOSAGE FORMS.

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ABSTRACT

Increasing knowledge and treatment of cardiovascular risk factors has led to a decline in mortality rates in developed countries however the problem continues to escalate globally because rates in developing countries are increasing rapidly. The Main Objective of this review is saying about the today's concept of vulnerable plaque has evolved primarily from the early pioneering work uncovering the pivotal role of plaque rupture and coronary thrombosis as the major cause of acute myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death. The delivery of the Nanoparticles directly into the blood stream to provide enhanced activity of the unstable plaque in the diagnosis of plaque rupture and may ultimately permit targeted delivery of therapies directly to the site of vascular injury. These nanoparticles as Orodispersable tablets have been successfully used in therapy and there is still no compendia method of their disintegration time. The oral route of administration continues to be the most preferred route due to its diverse advantages including ease of administration, precise dosage, self-medication, versatility and most importantly patient compliance. These methods of formulation shown that development of novel biorelevant methods of ODT's disintegration time determination is eligible. All these aspects should be taken into consideration during the novel methods development process.

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INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease is the most common cause of death worldwide in both men and women. As societies become more developed, and the standard of living improves, cardiovascular disease increases in prevalence as less people die early in life from communicable disease due to improvements in healthcare. Life expectancy also increases and cardiovascular disease is more common in older persons. Increasing knowledge and treatment of cardiovascular risk factors has led to a decline in mortality rates, however the problem continues to escalate globally because rates in developing countries are increasing rapidly. Successful therapies and strategies for prevention of cardiovascular disease are dependent on identification of individuals at risk using clinical risk scores based on age, sex, blood pressure, serum cholesterol and cigarette smoking [1]. The risk scores are used widely and identification of traditional risk factors is the basis of most primary prevention screening policies, many of persons presenting with an adverse cardiac event have no prior history or any established risk factors [2]. The converse is also true, many patients with risk factors do not go on to develop atherothrombotic disease or have an acute cardiovascular event.

Cardiovascular risk is not a static entity and fluctuates hour to hour and day to day. There are many contributing factors to our cardiovascular risk some of which are:

- Age
- Gender
- Physical Activity
- Genetics
- Diet
- Blood Cholesterol
- Blood Pressure
- Weight
- Stress
- Air Pollution

All these factors combine, at any one time, to determine how likely it is that an individual will suffer an adverse cardiovascular event.

Nanotechnology aims at the development of nanoparticles (particles with at least one dimension less than 100nm). Nanotechnology is currently being applied in all manner of commercial industries to confer unique properties on products or improve those existing ones. One of the potentially most significant applications is in the field of medicine is Nanotoxicity [3]. Nanotoxicology assesses the potential risks of both naturally occurring and anthropogenic nanoparticles, it serves to ensure the safety and continued development of nanotechnology whilst protecting consumers, workers and the environment [4]. The novel nature of Engineered Nano particles (ENPs) is not considered under American, European or British medical product legislation. Whilst we may come to realise in the future that it is unnecessary to legislate ENP separately a more cautious approach seems warranted during early use. This should avoid unexpected outcomes and increase public confidence in their safety when their use becomes widespread. Nanotechnology has advanced rapidly and is now a platform for many medical applications such as drug delivery [5] and diagnosis of disease. ENPs intended for clinical application should be rigorously tested with assessments taking into consideration the unique toxicology profile of nanoscale materials [6]. The diversity of medical ENPs with respect to size, surface area, composition and surface properties, and the rapid pace of their development and commercialization, poses significant challenges to traditional toxicological paradigms [7]. With so many variables and no agreed standards for safety it may be difficult to fully characterise the effects of ENPs before clinical use [8].

Diagnostic and therapeutic applications of nanoparticles in cardiovascular disease

Nanomaterial synthesis has progressed rapidly in recent years and has generated complex state-of-the-art nanoscale structures with diverse and complex functionalities. Some patients have difficulties in swallowing or chewing solid dosage which forms risk or fear of choking, so this is a major problem in the use of tablets.

Oral fast dissolving film is a new drug delivery system for oral delivery of drug. Oral fast dissolving film is a type of film which is used in acute condition such as pain, antiemetic, anti-migraine, anti-hypertension, congestive heart failure and asthma etc. Oral fast dissolving film has gained popularity due to its availability in various size, shape and intended to disintegrate or dissolve within seconds [9]. For fast dissolving active pharmaceutical ingredients absorption is possible through the oral mucosa and may improve bioavailability [10] Fast-dissolving drug-delivery systems came into existence in the late 1970's as an alternative to tablets, capsules and syrups for paediatric and geriatric patients who experience difficulties in swallowing traditional oral solid-dosage forms. These systems consist of the solid dosage forms that disintegrate and dissolve quickly in the oral cavity without the administration of water. Research and development in the oral drug delivery segment has led to transition of dosage forms from simple conventional tablets or capsules to modified release tablets or capsules to oral disintegrating tablet (ODT) to wafer to the recent development of oral fast dissolving films (OFDF). Among the plethora of avenues explored for the rapid drug releasing products, oral strip technology is gaining much attention. [11]

Figure 1: Three hypothetical pathways whereby nanoparticles that deposit in the lungs could impact the cardiovascular system and cause the impairments shown.

Figure 2: Cardiovascular impairments associated with pulmonary deposition of nanoparticles in epidemiological and experimental studies.

Advantages of Oral Fast Dissolving Films

1. Oral fast dissolving films can be administered without water, anywhere, any time.
2. Due to the presence of larger surface area, films provide rapid disintegrating and dissolution in the oral cavity.
3. Oral fast dissolving films are flexible and portable in nature so they provide ease in transportation, during consumer handling and storage.
4. Suitability for geriatric and pediatric patients, who experience difficulties in swallowing and for mentally ill.
5. Beneficial in cases such as motion sickness, acute pain, allergic attack or coughing, where an ultra-rapid onset of action required.
6. Stability for longer duration of time, since the drug remains in solid dosage form till it is consumed.
7. Bioavailability, as compared liquid formulations, precision in the administered dose is ensured from each strip of the film.
8. The oral or buccal mucosa being highly vascularized, drugs can be absorbed directly and can enter the systemic circulation without undergoing first- pass hepatic metabolism. This advantage can be exploited in preparing products with improved oral bioavailability of molecules that undergo first pass effect.
9. The sublingual and buccal delivery of a drug via thin film has the potential to improve the onset of action, lower the dosing, and enhance the efficacy and safety profile of the medicament.

Disadvantages

1. High doses cannot be incorporated.
2. Dose uniformity is a technical challenge.

Formulating Agents Employed in Oral Fast Dissolving Films

1. Active pharmaceutical ingredient.
2. Film forming polymers.
3. Plasticizer.
4. Sweetening agent.
5. Saliva stimulating agent.
6. Flavoring agent.
7. Coloring agent.

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient

A typical composition of the film contains 1-25% w/w of the drug. Small dose molecules are the best candidates to be incorporated in ODT. It is always useful to have micronized API which will improve the texture of the film and also for better dissolution and uniformity in the ODT. Thus, before incorporating the API in the ODT, the taste needs to be masked. Various methods can be used to improve the palatability of the formulation. Among the techniques employed, the simplest method involves the mixing and Co- processing of bitter tasting API with excipients with pleasurable taste. This is often termed as obscuration technique [12].

Film Forming Polymer

Since the primary use of all thin film oral dosage forms relies on their disintegration in the saliva of the oral cavity, the final film that is used must necessarily be water soluble. The polymers can be used alone or in combination to improve hydrophilicity, flexibility, mouth-feel and solubility characteristics of fast dissolving films. The stiffness of the strip depends on the type of polymer and the amount of polymer in the formulation. Polyvinyl pyrrolidone films are brittle in nature and therefore crospovidone is mixed with poly vinyl pyrrolidone for preparation of flexible fast disintegrating films. Combination of microcrystalline cellulose and maltodextrin has been used to formulate fast dissolving films of piroxicam made by hot melt extrusion technique. In this case, microcrystalline cellulose is used to render the film non-sticky and smooth. Microcrystalline cellulose was also used to decrease the disintegration time and improve the dissolution of drug from the films. Water soluble polymer that may be used include natural gums such as those derived from guar, xanthan, acacia, Arabic or tragacanth, Other available polymers are, polyethylene oxide, acrylic based polymer and several types of sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), several types of hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC), a synthetic copolymer of polyethylene glycol– polyvinyl alcohol and sodium alginate [13].

Plasticizer

Plasticizer is a vital ingredient of the fast dissolving films. Plasticizer helps to improve the flexibility of the strip and reduces the brittleness of the films [14]. It significantly improves the film forming properties by reducing the glass transition temperature of the polymer. The chemical structure and concentration of plasticizers play an important role in alleviating the glass transition temperature of the polymers. The flow of polymer will get better with the use of plasticizer and enhances the strength of the polymer. Glycerol, Propylene glycol, low molecular weight polyethylene glycols, phthalate derivatives like dimethyl, diethyl and dibutyl phthalate, citrate derivatives such as tributyl, triethyl, acetyl citrate, triacetin and castor oil are some of the commonly used plasticizer excipients. Typically, the plasticizers are used in the concentration of 0–20 percent; w/w of dry polymer weight. However, inappropriate use of plasticizer may lead to film cracking, splitting and peeling of the strip. It is also reported that the use of certain plasticizers may also affect the absorption rate of the drug.

Sweetening Agents

Sweeteners have become the important part of the formulation intended to be disintegrated or dissolved in the oral cavity. Generally, sweeteners are used in the concentration of 3 to 6% w/w either alone or in combination. Both natural sweeteners as well as artificial sweeteners are used in the formulation of these fast dissolving films [15]. Polyhydric alcohols such as sorbitol, mannitol can be used in combination as they additionally provide good mouthfeel and cooling sensation. However, it should be noted that the use of natural sugars in such preparations need to be restricted in people who are on diet or in the case of diabetic patients.

Saliva Stimulating Agent

The purpose of using saliva stimulating agents is to increase the rate of production of saliva that would aid in the faster disintegration of the rapid dissolving strip formulations [16]. Generally, acids which are used in the preparation of food can be utilized as salivary stimulants. E.g. Citric acid, malic acid, lactic acid, ascorbic acid and tartaric acid. These agents are used alone or in combination between 2 to 6% w/w of weight of the strip.

Flavouring Agents

Preferably up to 10% w/w flavours are added in the ODT formulations. The acceptance of the oral disintegrating or dissolving formulation by an individual is largely depends on the initial flavour quality which is observed in first few seconds after the product has been consumed and the after taste of the formulation which lasts for at least about 10 mins. The selection of flavour is dependent on the type of drug to be incorporated in the formulation. It was observed that age plays a significant role in the taste fondness. The geriatric population like mint or orange flavours while younger generation like flavour like fruit punch, raspberry etc. Flavouring agents can be selected from synthetic flavour oils, oleo resins, extract derived from various parts of the plants like leaves, fruits and flowers.

Methods of Preparation of Oral Fast Dissolving Films

One or more of the following process can be used to manufacture the oral fast dissolving films.

1. Solvent casting
2. Semisolid casting.
3. Hot melt extrusion.
4. Solid dispersion extrusion.
5. Rolling method.

Solvent Casting Method

In solvent casting method excipients are dissolved in water, then water soluble polymers and in last drug is added and stirred to form homogeneous solution. Finally solution is casted in to the Petri plate and dried [17].

Semisolid Casting

This method is preferably adopted when acid insoluble polymers are to be used in the preparation of the films. In Semisolid casting method gel mass is casted in to the films or ribbons using heat controlled drums. Gel mass is obtained by adding solution of film forming to a solution of acid insoluble polymer in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. Acid-insoluble polymers used to prepare films include: cellulose acetate phthalate, cellulose acetate butyrate. Acid insoluble polymer and film forming polymer should be used in the ratio of 1:4 [18].

Hot Melt Extrusion

In hot melt extrusion method, firstly the drug is mixed with carriers in solid form. Then dried granular material is introduced into the extruder. The screw speed should set at 15 rpm in order to process the granules inside the barrel of the extruder for approximately 3– 4 min. The processing temperatures should be 8000C (zone 1), 11500C (zone 2), 10000C (zone 3) and 6500C (zone 4). The extrudate (T = 6500C) then pressed into a cylindrical calendar in order to obtain a film. There are certain benefits of hot melt extrusion [19,20].

1. Fewer operation units.
2. Better content uniformity.
3. An anhydrous process.

Solid Dispersion Extrusion

In this method, immiscible components are extrude with drug and then solid dispersions are prepared. Finally, the solid dispersions are shaped into films by means of dies.

Rolling Method

In rolling method, a solution or suspension of drug with film forming polymer is prepared and subjected to the roller. The solution or suspension should have specific rheological consideration. The solvent is mainly water and mixture of water and alcohol. The film is dried on the rollers and cutted in to desired shapes and sizes [21].

Evaluation of Oro dispersible Films

Morphology Study

The morphology of the films is studies using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), at definite magnification.

Weight Variations

Weight variation is studies by individually weighing 10 randomly selected films and calculating the average weight. The average weight should not deviate significantly from the average weight.

Thickness

The thickness of film is determined by screw gauge or micrometer at different points of the films.

Drug Content

A film of size was cut and put in 10 ml of volumetric flask which containing solvent. This was then shaken in a mechanical shaker for 2 hrs to get a homogeneous solution and filtered. The drug was determined spectroscopically by appropriate dilution [22].

Disintegration Test

Determined manually by dipping the film in 10 ml of water in beaker with gently shaking when film was dissolved, time was noted.

In Vitro Drug Release

Dissolution testing can be performed using the standard basket or paddle apparatus described in any of the pharmacopoeia. The dissolution medium will essentially be selected as per the sink conditions and highest dose of the API. Many times the dissolution test can be difficult due to tendency of the strip to float onto the dissolution medium when the paddle apparatus is employed.

Stability Studies

Stability study was carried out for all the batches at accelerated condition 65% relative humidity and 35°C (temperature) in the humidity chamber for the three months. After 3 months, the films were evaluated for the drug content, disintegration time and physical appearance observation.

Packaging

A variety of packaging options are available for fast dissolving films. single packaging is mandatory for films. Which are pharmaceutical products; an aluminium pouch is the most commonly used packaging format. The rapid card is the same size as a credit card and holds three mouth dissolving films on each side. Every dose can be taken out individually, allowing the patient to carry six singles, packaged doses of his medication in his purse or wallet and have it readily available.

Applications of Oral Fast Dissolving Films

Oral mucosal delivery via buccal, sublingual and mucosal route could become a preferential delivery method for therapies in which rapid absorption is desired. Including those used to manage pain, allergies, sleep difficulties and central nervous system disorders.

Topical Applications

The use of oral fast dissolvable films may be feasible in the delivery of active agents such as analgesics or antimicrobials ingredients for wound care and other applications.

Gastro Retentive Dosage System

Oral fast dissolvable films are being considered in dosage forms for which water soluble and poorly soluble molecules of various molecular weights are contained in a film format. [8] Dissolution of the films could be triggered by the PH or enzyme secretions of the gastrointestinal tract and could potentially be used to treat gastrointestinal disorders [23,24].

Diagnostic Devices

Dissolvable devices may be loaded with sensitive reagents to allow controlled release when exposed to a biological fluid or to create isolation barriers for separating multiple reagents to enable a timed reaction within a diagnostic device. Therefore, other alternative tests reflecting more or less in vivo conditions of ODTs disintegration in the human mouth were proposed. In this study, we compared some of these methods with the results achieved with our own-construction apparatus as well as in vivo disintegration time [25,26]. The applied methods could be divided into three groups in regard to the forces acting on the tablets during the tests. Disintegration of tablets in the human mouth is caused by several factors. Water from saliva causes swelling and deformation of the tablet mass through the capillary action [27]. The pressure of the tongue causes squeezing and grinding of the tablet between the surface of the tongue and the upper palate [28]. The tablet mass can also be partially or completely dissolved in the saliva depending on the excipients and pharmaceutical substance used [29]. It mainly occurs in the case of lyophilized formulations containing water soluble drug substances, and causes their disintegration in a matter of seconds. On the other hand, ODTs prepared by the direct compression method usually contain at least some excipients poorly soluble in water, and the dissolution is less important in the mechanism of their disintegration [30]. The collection of this data would be relatively straightforward and provide a very meaningful method of monitoring the long-term effects of introducing huge numbers of ENPs into patients with underlying inflammatory conditions.

The Main Objective of this review is saying about the today's concept of vulnerable plaque has evolved primarily from the early pioneering work uncovering the pivotal role of plaque rupture and coronary thrombosis as the major cause of acute myocardial infarction and sudden cardiac death. Since the first historical description of plaque rupture in 1844, several key studies by leading researchers and clinicians have lead to the current accepted views on lesion instability. Important to the complex paradigm of plaque destabilization and thrombosis are many discoveries beginning with the earliest descriptions of advanced plaques, reminiscent of abscesses encapsulated by fibrous tissue capable of rupture. It was not until the late 1980s that studies of remodelling provided keen insight into the growth of advanced plaques, beyond the simple accumulation of lipid. The emphasis in the next decade, however, was on a focused shift toward the mechanisms of lesion vulnerability based on the contribution of tissue proteolysis by matrix metalloproteinases as an essential factor responsible for thinning and rupture of the fibrous cap. To unify the understanding of what constitutes a vulnerable plaque, morphological studies, mostly from autopsy, suggest the importance of necrotic core size, inflammation, and fibrous cap thickness. Definitive proof of the vulnerable plaque, however, remains elusive because animal or human data supporting a cause-and-effect relationship are lacking. The delivery of the Nanoparticles directly into the blood stream to provide enhanced activity of the unstable plaque in the diagnosis of plaque rupture and may ultimately permit targeted delivery of therapies directly to the site of vascular injury. These nanoparticles as Orodispersable tablets have been successfully used in therapy and there is still no compendia method of their disintegration time. These methods of formulation shown that development of novel biorelevant methods of ODT's disintegration time determination is eligible. All these aspects should be taken into consideration during the novel methods development process.

CONCLUSION

The current understanding of particle formation by rapid precipitation and subsequent stabilization makes a nanoparticulate technology that can be exploited for several applications and high loading efficiencies, control of particle size and flexibility in incorporating multiple activities. It was observed that the engineered nanoparticles are a state-of-art technology that requires a suitable technique among the various possible methods. The drug loaded nanoparticles now can be produced by simple, safe and reproducible techniques available. Depending on the physicochemical characteristics of a drug, it is possible to choose the best method of preparation and the polymer to produce nanoparticles with the desired size range with good entrapment efficiency of the drug. These Nanoparticle formation opportunities for a wide range of activities and scope of applications can be beneficial. These studies aimed to resolve a potentially important in medical therapeutics in the cardiovascular system even at relatively low concentrations and at high concentrations in patients with unstable atherothrombotic disease. As a result, field develops more attention should be given to assay the potential toxicity of novel agents like engineered nanoparticles. This review has shown that the development of novel methods of ODTs disintegrating time measurements is eligible. Particularly, it is important to develop, methods that better reflect conditions in the oral cavity. The volume of medium, its temperature, and the type of forces acting on the tablet during a disintegration test are all important factors affecting the disintegration process. All these aspects should be taken into consideration during the novel methods development process. Despite these technological challenges, nanoparticles have been showed great promise for the development of drug delivery system.

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